

Spatial Updating in Virtual Reality for Reproducing Object Locations in Vista Space – Boundaries, Landmarks, and Idiothetic Cues

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11 **Abstract**

12 Keeping track of locations across self-motion is possible by continuously updating spatial
13 representations or by encoding and later instantaneously retrieving spatial representations. In virtual
14 reality (VR), sensory cues to self-motion used in continuous updating are typically reduced. In
15 passive translation compared to real walking in VR, optic flow is available but body-based
16 (idiothetic) cues are missing. With both kinds of translation, boundaries and landmarks as static
17 visual cues can be used for instantaneous updating. In two experiments, we let participants encode
18 two target locations, one of which had to be reproduced by pointing after forward translation in
19 immersive VR (HMD). We increased sensory cues to self-motion in comparison to passive
20 translation either by strengthening optic flow or by real walking. Furthermore, we varied static visual
21 cues in the form of boundaries and landmarks inside boundaries. Increased optic flow and real
22 walking did not reliably increase performance suggesting that optic flow even in a sparse
23 environment was sufficient for continuous updating or that merely instantaneous updating took place.
24 Boundaries and landmarks, however, did support performance as quantified by decreased bias and
25 increased precision, particularly if they were close to or even enclosed target locations. Thus,
26 enriched spatial context is a viable method to support spatial updating in VR and synthetic
27 environments (teleoperation). Spatial context does not only provide static visual reference in offline
28 updating and continuous allocentric self-location updating but according to recent neuroscientific
29 evidence on egocentric bearing cells, contributes to continuous egocentric location updating as well.

30 **1 Introduction**

31 While moving through an environment, the own location and orientation within the environment as
32 well as attended egocentric location representations are effortlessly updated. For instance, imagine
33 yourself walking on a sidewalk and having noticed a small box 20m ahead on the other side of the
34 street. If a stopping bus occluded the box and you continued walking, you could still point to the box.
35 If the box would be gone after the bus had moved on, you could point to the former location of the
36 box from your novel standpoint because the egocentric memory representation of the box location
37 needed for pointing has been updated while you walked forward. Such updating happens effortlessly

38 for a low number of object locations when walking in the real world (e.g., Attneave & Farrar, 1977).
39 In virtual reality (VR), however, cues about self-motion that are processed in spatial updating are
40 reduced. In the experiments reported here, we studied strengthened optic flow and idiothetic (body-
41 based) cues potentially supporting spatial updating of encoded locations across forward self-motion
42 in VR. In addition to dynamic cues about self-motion, we also varied static visual cues that as spatial
43 reference can serve self-localization and thus egocentric object-location updating as well as
44 allocentric encoding and reproducing of object locations. If the box on the sidewalk had been located
45 in front of a store window or close to a fire hydrant, these elements of spatial context would have
46 provided reference in encoding and had supported in reproducing the box location. We quantify such
47 supporting effects of boundaries and landmarks on spatial memory across forward self-motion in VR
48 as decreased bias and increased precision.

49 **2 Literature review and research questions**

50 **2.1 Continuous and instantaneous updating**

51 Imagine a sparse environment, say a sand surface in a desert. You throw a coin ahead of you and then
52 a second one. They disappear in the sand. After a few steps forward, you can still point to the coins.
53 Their egocentric representations have been continuously updated. If you had walked forward with
54 your eyes closed, this would have happened by dynamic, non-visual, body-based (idiothetic) cues
55 alone. Continuous updating of the ego-location while walking is commonly called path integration
56 and enables to point to egocentrically encoded locations after self-motion. With open eyes, dynamic
57 visual information (optic flow) contributes to continuous updating of the ego-location and thus also
58 to continuous updating of egocentric location representations. In an environment that contains
59 boundaries and landmarks, optic flow is strengthened and continuous updating of the ego-location is
60 supported by the spatial reference that they provide both for self-localization in egocentric as well as
61 allocentric representations of the environment.

62 With spatial reference (i.e., in an environment that is not sparse), both the ego-location in an
63 environment and previously encoded but now invisible target locations can be determined after self-
64 motion by instantaneous updating. Particularly if a target location is close to a boundary or landmark,
65 the egocentric representation required for pointing to the target location can be constructed after self-
66 motion instantaneously. For example, imagine that one of the coins had disappeared in the sand close
67 to a rock. The rock and thus the invisible target location are obvious after self-motion and
68 instantaneous updating for pointing is trivial.

69 The two ways of retrieving locations after self-motion - based on continuous and on instantaneous
70 updating (von der Heyde & Riecke, 2002) - usually are both possible to employ but the degree to
71 which available cues support either is variable and particularly so across VR scenarios. For example,
72 in VR idiothetic cues supporting continuous updating are missing if self-motion is just simulated but
73 available if real self-motion happens in parallel. Furthermore, VR environments can be sparse with
74 only little spatial reference or they can provide rich spatial context encompassing boundaries and
75 landmarks that supports continuous and instantaneous updating. Spatial reference close to target
76 locations is particularly valuable for instantaneous updating of egocentric target location memory.

77 **2.2 Dynamic and static visual and non-visual cues**

78 Visual and non-visual cues are contributing to spatial updating in the real world (Gallistel, 1990). As
79 dynamic visual information, optic flow signals self-motion while self-motion takes place and
80 supports continuous spatial updating. As static visual cues, boundaries and landmarks support

81 instantaneous spatial updating. They afford encoding distances and directions to oneself, among
82 them, and to other objects at any time (McNamara, 2013). Instantaneous spatial updating enables
83 locating oneself instantly within an environment, for example, when waking up in a moving vehicle,
84 when putting on a head-mounted display (HMD), or after teleportation in VR. Locations encoded
85 with reference to static landmarks can also be instantaneously updated by updating or (re-
86)establishing the respective egocentric location representation (the box next to the fire hydrant or the
87 buried coin next to the rock).

88 Continuous spatial updating during self-motion in the real world is usually supported not only by
89 optic flow but in addition by non-visual cues. These non-visual cues encompass vestibular
90 information, proprioceptive information, and motor efference, and are referred to as body-based or
91 idiothetic cues (Jeffery & O’Keefe, 1999; Chrastil & Warren, 2012). Idiothetic cues to self-motion
92 allow for continuous spatial updating when optic flow is unavailable, for example, with closed eyes
93 or in complete darkness (Loomis et al., 1993).

94 Continuously updating the ego-location and ego-orientation in navigation based on self-motion cues
95 (including idiothetic cues and optic flow) is commonly called path integration, instantaneously
96 determining and updating ego-location and orientation with reference to static visual cues is named
97 piloting. Research on self-localization and navigation in VR pertains to the updating of egocentric
98 representations of locations. Generally, in sparse environments (or darkness or in a moving crowd),
99 updating egocentric representations (self to environment and self to object) for reproducing object
100 locations after self-motion is particularly important compared to the alternative of using encoded
101 allocentric (object to environment) relations (cf. Cheng et al., 2007).

102 **2.3 Passive and active translation and rotation in virtual reality**

103 Translation denotes self-motion that changes the ego-location in an environment, rotation denotes
104 changing heading direction even without changing location. When being translated or rotated
105 passively in VR without actual body movement, optic flow is available but idiothetic cues to self-
106 motion are missing. Rotation passively experienced in VR and thus without idiothetic cues results in
107 marked performance impairments in tasks testing for the updating of spatial representations across
108 self-motion compared with conditions, in which rotation is actively performed (Chance et al., 1998;
109 Klatzky, Loomis et al., 1998; Kearns et al., 2002; Ruddle & Lessels, 2006; Cherep et al., 2020; Kelly
110 et al., 2022; Wraga, Creem-Regehr, & Proffitt, 2004; for an exception in a rich VR environment see
111 Riecke et al., 2007).

112 A common spatial updating task that involves rotation and translation is triangle completion, which
113 requires navigating back to the starting location after traveling two outward legs of a triangle (or
114 more than two legs, e.g., Kelly et al., 2008). For instance, Kearns et al. (2002) let participants who
115 wore an HMD perform a triangle completion task in VR and compared joystick-controlled
116 locomotion with real walking. They found clearly superior performance for real walking. A second
117 common task informing about the precision of spatial updating is pointing to a location after
118 movement. Participants may be asked to point to or orient towards the starting location (e.g., Klatzky
119 et al., 1998), which highlights the similarity of pointing with triangle completion (Wang, 2017).
120 Instead of pointing to the starting location, pointing after movement can ask for pointing to locations
121 of objects that are no longer visible at the time of testing (e.g., pointing after passive forward
122 translation in Wolbers et al., 2008). For pointing to object locations after movement that
123 encompassed rotation and translation, the superiority of real walking compared to joystick-controlled
124 locomotion in VR wearing an HMD has been demonstrated, for example, by Chance et al. (1998).

125 While being passively rotated impairs performance reliably, mere passive translation is not
126 consistently detrimental. Passive translation combined with real rotation can result in similar
127 performance as real walking (Klatzky et al., 1998; Riecke et al., 2010; Barhorst-Cates et al., 2021) or
128 at least in better performance than if both translation and rotation are joystick-controlled (Chance et
129 al., 1998). Optic flow during translation is critical, however: teleportation impairs spatial updating
130 consistently (Barhorst-Cates et al., 2021; Cherep et al., 2020; Kelly et al., 2022)

131 Passive translation in sparse environments may be easier to account for in updating than passive
132 rotation (e.g., in reproducing the location of a target object) either because continuous online
133 updating needs less sensory cues for translation than for rotation or because instantaneous offline
134 updating is easier for translation than rotation (Hodgson & Waller, 2006). It may be easier in forward
135 translation because the egocentric reference frame remains aligned with encoded object-to-object
136 relations (or more generally, an allocentric reference frame). Offline updating of a target location
137 after translation can then be performed by determining the current self-location within the allocentric
138 frame and the line connecting the self with the target location. The orientation of this line is the
139 direction for pointing to the target location. The distance for pointing can be determined by
140 imagining a parallel to the forward axis through the target location in the allocentric frame and
141 locating its intersection with the pointing direction. Such use of aligned egocentric and allocentric
142 representations also explains that updating for merely imagined translation is much easier than for
143 imagined rotation (Presson & Montello, 1994; Rieser, 1989).

144 But passive translation may also be easier to process than passive rotation just because continuous
145 spatial updating for forward translation needs less sensory cues and can succeed with optic flow
146 alone. Whether optic flow in passive translation is sufficient for continuous spatial updating for
147 forward translation is interesting for interpreting fMRI results obtained with participants seeing optic
148 flow suggesting forward translation while lying supine in an MRI scanner and performing a spatial
149 memory and pointing task similar to the one employed in the present experiments (Wolbers et al.,
150 2008). If optic flow alone would be sufficient and idiothetic cues by real walking would not improve
151 performance, this would support the claim that this and similar fMRI studies inform about brain
152 activation in spatial updating in real scenarios. Succeeding continuous spatial updating driven by
153 optic flow during passive translation would directly provide the novel egocentric location of the
154 target object. In any case, continuous spatial updating should reliably succeed if it is driven
155 additionally by idiothetic cues from real walking during active translation. Thus, richer sensory cues
156 could improve spatial updating across forward self-motion in VR.

157 In Experiment 1, we tested for an effect of pronounced optic flow during passive translation on
158 pointing performance in reproducing object locations after self-motion, and in Experiment 2, we
159 tested for an effect of real walking comparing passive and active translation. To preview our results
160 on these manipulations, we did not find reliable performance improvements from increased optic
161 flow and real walking compared to passive translation. In addition, we studied effects of landmarks
162 and boundaries as static visual cues that provide reference for locating oneself as well as for encoding
163 object locations (and that – present in the field of view during self-motion – also increase optic flow).

164 **2.4 Landmarks and boundaries**

165 Landmarks and boundaries, for instance static objects, corners, texture borders, and walls, provide
166 spatial reference for self-localization and for encoding and reproducing target locations. Particularly
167 in familiar environments, humans can determine their location and the egocentric relations to (earlier
168 encoded) object locations by estimating distance and bearing to visible reference. Such instantaneous

169 spatial updating is also employed to correct for otherwise cumulating error in continuous spatial
170 updating (Ekstrom et al., 2018).

171 Encoding and updating occur in parallel in allocentric and egocentric reference frames (Byrne et al.,
172 2007; Mou et al., 2004). Boundaries and landmarks provide the spatial context for allocentric self-
173 localization, updating, and episodic spatial memory as extensively documented by neuroscientific
174 findings on place cells, grid cells, boundary vector cells, and head direction cells in animals and
175 humans (Evans et al., 2016). More recently, neuroscientific evidence accumulated for egocentric self-
176 localization and updating as well: Corresponding to recent findings in animal studies and to
177 predictions of neurocomputational models of human spatial cognition, single cell recordings in
178 humans have documented egocentric bearing cells prevalent in parahippocampal cortex (Kunz et al.,
179 2021). In the experiments, participants navigated with arrow keys within a circular boundary
180 surrounded by landmarks in a virtual environment experienced on a laptop screen while performing a
181 spatial memory task. The firing rates of egocentric bearing cells encoded the egocentric direction
182 toward reference points in the present spatial context. For instance, the firing rate could be
183 particularly high if the reference point was located to the left from the current heading direction.
184 Some egocentric bearing cells did not just code for egocentric direction but also for egocentric
185 distance and thus supported a vectorial egocentric representation of the local environment. Of
186 particular interest for the present study, the tuning of egocentric bearing cells persisted during passive
187 self-motion in the virtual environment, which presumably provides a neural mechanism for
188 egocentric continuous spatial updating in the local spatial context of a visually rich environment even
189 without idiothetic cues.

190 Landmarks and boundaries constitute spatial context for encoding and updating in allocentric and
191 egocentric reference frames. Compared to an open field, boundaries can alleviate the impairment by
192 missing idiothetic cues when a triangle completion task is performed in VR with teleportation
193 (Cherap et al., 2020). Objects as landmarks that were located at the boundary have been found to
194 further improve performance in a triangle completion task (Kelly et al., 2022). Boundaries have been
195 compared to landmarks in spatial learning with the presumption that they may be processed
196 fundamentally different in spatial memory (Doeller & Burgess, 2008), however, the currently
197 available evidence rather supports the view that both function as environmental cues contributing to
198 spatial context (Buckley et al., 2021).

199 Shapes of boundaries and configurations of landmarks can cause and influence biases in spatial
200 memory and updating (McNamara, 2013; Kelly et al., 2008; Kelly et al., 2013; Zhou & Mou, 2019).
201 For instance, in a recent spatial memory experiment in VR, either a rectangular boundary consisting
202 of three walls or three traffic cones as landmarks (located at the center points of the walls and
203 forming a triangle) were provided as spatial context (Negen et al., 2020). Participants were teleported
204 to a new and rotated viewpoint between encoding and retrieval. Raw average error did not differ
205 between conditions, but the observed bias pattern in retrieved target locations differed between the
206 walls (rectangle) and the cones (triangle) conditions. With walls, the target locations were retrieved
207 with biases towards a point in front of the center of the front wall. With cones as landmarks, the
208 target locations were retrieved with biases towards a point at the center of the triangle formed by the
209 cones and slightly more distant from the front cone. In both conditions, the biases were the stronger
210 the more distant a target location was from the respective point. We studied such boundary and
211 landmark effects on bias and precision in more detail.

212 In Experiment 1, we tested for effects of a (partial) boundary and landmarks at the boundary by
213 presenting a lateral wall containing distinctive local features that could function as landmarks. In

214 Experiment 2, we were interested in comparing boundaries with landmarks closer to target locations
215 (inside the boundary) and in combined effects of boundaries and such landmarks (cue combination).
216 We presumed that landmarks closer to target locations could compensate the lack of idiothetic cues
217 across passive self-motion in VR even more effectively than boundaries. Furthermore, in Experiment
218 2, we varied boundary shape (rectangle, trapezoid, ellipse) comparing shapes with and without
219 vertices that can function as landmarks, and shapes with sides parallel to or oblique to the forward
220 axis of translation. Thus, we varied spatial context in its richness that is presumably important for
221 supporting continuous updating and by the number and proximity of landmarks to targets in its
222 usefulness for instantaneous updating.

223 **3 Experiment 1 – Lateral wall as reference and sleepers for optic flow**

224 In Experiment 1, participants encoded two target locations in immersive VR, experienced passive
225 forward translation, and reproduced one target location by pointing. We varied visual cues that
226 potentially could support in updating. A stripe pattern resembling railway sleepers presented
227 overhead only during translation was intended to increase optic flow. A lateral wall with distinctive
228 local features was intended to provide spatial reference particularly for encoding and reproducing
229 target locations close to the lateral wall. We assessed updating performance by distance error, bias,
230 and precision.

231 **3.1 Materials and methods**

232 **3.1.1 Participants**

233 Thirty-two students of Chemnitz University of Technology (15 men, 17 women) with a mean age of
234 25.36 years ($SD = 4.84$) participated in two sessions separated by 1 to 3 days ($M = 1.41$, $SD = 0.70$)
235 that lasted approximately 90 min each. They fulfilled part of a curricular requirement or received
236 monetary compensation (30 Euro). Two additional participants did not complete the experiment
237 because of VR motion sickness. The data of four additional participants were excluded because of
238 technical or experimenter error that caused incomplete or unbalanced datasets. The data and analysis
239 scripts are publicly available: <https://osf.io/e39jf/>.

240 **3.1.2 Design**

241 All experimental factors were varied within-subjects. Trials with translation (Translation) and trials
242 without translation (No Translation) were intermixed. In Translation trials, either overhead sleepers
243 were shown during translation or not (Sleepers, No Sleepers). The environment either was sparse (No
244 Wall) or contained a lateral wall that was presented either left or right. To-be-reproduced target
245 locations were also either left or right and consequently were close (Same Side) or distant (Opposite)
246 to a lateral wall. For Translation trials, this resulted in a 2 x 3 factorial within-subjects design
247 including the factors Sleepers (Sleepers, No Sleepers) and Wall (Same Side, Opposite, No Wall). For
248 No Translation trials, the design was one-factorial within-subjects with the three-level factor Wall
249 (Same Side, Opposite, No Wall).

250 Performance in reproducing target locations was quantified by the mean absolute Euclidean distance
251 between the indicated and the actual target location on the floor plane (absolute distance error), by
252 the mean signed distances on the x-axis and on the forward y-axis (response bias), and by the
253 standard deviations of the distances on the x-axis and on the forward y-axis (lower values indicating
254 higher precision).

255 **3.1.3 Apparatus and stimuli**

256 The virtual environment was presented stereoscopically in an Oculus Quest head-mounted display
257 (HMD) with a resolution of 1,440 x 1,600 pixels per eye (71 Hz frame rate, 94° x 94° field of view).
258 Tracking of the HMD and a hand-held controller used a combination of inside-out tracking by four
259 cameras and sensors including a gyroscope and acceleration sensors. Unity and the Oculus Link were
260 used to render images on a Notebook with the Intel i7 processor and a NVIDIA Quadro RTX 3000
261 graphics card.

262 The virtual environment was an open field scene with a light ochre sand-textured floor plane
263 extending to the horizon under a cloudless atmospheric blue sky (Figure 1). The participant's
264 perspective was set at a height of 180 cm. The participant at coordinates (0, 0) on the left-right and
265 front-back axes, respectively, was oriented towards a pair of 7m high poles visible ahead at (-5 m, 40
266 m) and (5 m, 40 m). In the No Wall condition, these were the only reference objects in the
267 environment. In the trials with a lateral wall (Same Side, Opposite), a 2 m high brick wall extended
268 parallel to the forward axis 11 m to the left or to the right of the participant almost up to the poles
269 ending at (-11 m, 31 m) or (11 m, 31 m), respectively. 12 different wall shapes (mirrored for left and
270 right versions) were constructed by attaching flat columns of varying height at intervals of around 5
271 m at the side facing the participant creating protrusions and crenels. In the Sleepers condition, a
272 cross-striped rectangular surface that extended as a band overhead the participant to the poles was
273 presented during forward translation to strengthen optic flow. The sleepers band was 4.6 m wide at a
274 height of 4.2 m with stripes of 0.2 m alternating in light and dark gray. In trials with translation, the
275 passive forward translation was 7, 8, or 9 m.

276 Objects at target locations were red cross shapes (1.5 m x 1.5 m) with bars of breadth 0.4 m and
277 height 0.25 m. In each trial, two such target objects were presented, one to the left and one to the
278 right of the central forward axis. Thus, in trials with a lateral wall, one was close to a wall (Same
279 Side) that provided spatial reference for encoding and reproducing the location and one was distant to
280 a wall (Opposite). Target locations were drawn from bivariate Gaussian distributions (SDs 1 m)
281 centered at four points on the left (L1, L2, L3, L4) and at four corresponding points at the right (R1,
282 R2, R3, R4) shown in Figure 2 and Table 1. All pairs were non-symmetric (e.g., L1 and R2, but not
283 L1 and R1).

284 The participants responded with the tracked controller. They directed an orange laser beam and a red
285 wireframe model of a target object that was presented where the laser beam intersected with the floor
286 plane. At the laser beam 1.3 m from the controller, an arrow pointing to the right or to the left
287 indicated which target location should be marked by placing the wireframe model.

288 **3.1.4 Procedure**

289 Upon arrival for the first session, the participant was informed about the procedure of both sessions
290 and signed informed consent. The experimenter provided instructions on how to put on the head-
291 mounted display (spatial distancing during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic). The participant stood
292 upright while wearing the HMD and held the controller in the right hand.

293 The task was introduced with 12 training trials with feedback followed by 12 training trials without
294 feedback. Training trials were balanced with regard to conditions and stimuli. The participant started
295 a trial by pressing the trigger button on the controller (operated by the index finger). After a black
296 blank screen shown for 200 ms, an auditory signal was played and two target objects were presented
297 in the virtual environment for 5 s, which then sank into the ground during 2s. In trials without

298 translation, the scene without the targets remained static for 7 s. In trials with translation, the scene
299 without the targets remained static for 7 s followed by the passive forward translation lasting 3500,
300 4000, or 4500 ms for 7, 8, and 9 m, respectively. Subsequently, a second auditory signal marked the
301 start of the response interval during which the laser beam with the red wireframe cross and the arrow
302 identifying the target location to be indicated were shown until the participant responded with
303 pressing the controller button. The laser beam and arrow disappeared and the placed wireframe
304 remained visible for 1500 ms. Then, the viewpoint was set back to the starting location and a
305 message window prompting to start the next trial was shown hovering in front of the poles with the
306 wireframe still visible on the ground. In training trials with feedback, the target objects were shown
307 after the response together with the placed wireframe. In trials with sleepers, the stripe pattern was
308 shown during the translation interval.

309 Separated in two sessions, participants responded once for each of the 8 target locations in each
310 possible combination of condition levels. There were 24 combinations when discerning lateral wall
311 placement left and right which determines whether a target location is close or distant to a wall: 6
312 (NoWall, Same Side, Opposite, NoWall/Sleepers, Same Side/Sleepers, Opposite/Sleepers) x 4
313 (translation 0, 7, 8, 9 m). Please, note that at translation 0, sleepers were never shown. This resulted
314 in 192 (8 x 24) experimental trials in total, which were presented in 8 blocks (4 blocks in the first and
315 4 blocks in the second session) and in pseudorandomized order ensuring that condition levels were
316 distributed evenly across the trial sequence, condition levels did not repeat more than once in
317 subsequent trials, and that no more than two subsequent to-be-reproduced target locations were on
318 the same side. Between blocks, participants took the HMD off for a break.

319 When returning to the lab for the second session, the participant first took computerized mental
320 rotation and spatial orientation tests at a laptop (not further reported). Then, the participant was
321 offered to repeat training trials before working through 4 blocks of experimental trials following the
322 same procedure as in the first session.

323 **3.2 Results**

324 Trials were retained for analysis if responses were to the correct side, pointing error was not higher
325 than 6 m of absolute Euclidean distance from the target location, and response time was less than 8 s
326 (98% of all trials). In repeated-measures ANOVAs, *F*-values have been Greenhouse-Geisser
327 corrected where necessary.

328 **3.2.1 Absolute distance error**

329 Mean absolute distance error in trials with translation did not differ between trials with targets to the
330 left and to the right (no reliable main effect of target side, $F(1, 31) = 2.30, p = .14$, and no reliable
331 two- or three-way interaction of the sleepers and the lateral wall manipulations with target side, all F s
332 < 1.47 , all $ps > .24$). As shown on the left in Figure 2, mean absolute distance error in translation
333 trials was smallest with a lateral wall at the Same Side. It slightly increased from Same Side to No
334 Wall when No Sleepers were shown and was slightly decreased with Sleepers in Opposite and No
335 Wall conditions. In a repeated-measures ANOVA, neither the main effects of Sleepers, $F(1, 31) =$
336 $1.28, p = .27, \eta_p^2 = .04$, and the lateral wall manipulation, $F(2, 62) = 1.07, p = .33, \eta_p^2 = .03$, nor the
337 interaction effect, $F(2, 62) = 0.83, p = .44, \eta_p^2 = .03$, were reliable. In the No Wall condition, the
338 Sleepers effect was largest, but unreliable as well, paired t-test $t(31) = 1.48, p = .15, d = 0.20$.

339 Mean absolute distance error in trials without translation is shown on the right in Figure 2 and also
340 increased slightly from Same Side to No Wall. In a repeated-measures ANOVA, the effect of the

341 lateral wall manipulation was unreliable, $F(2, 62) = 2.87, p = .07, \eta_p^2 = .09$. The effect of a lateral
342 wall on the Same Side vs. No Wall was $d = 0.27$, paired t-test $t(31) = 1.78, p = .09$ to quantify the
343 largest difference.

344 3.2.2 Bias and precision

345 For the subsequent analysis of response bias (signed distance error) and response precision in
346 translation trials, first, data were collapsed across translation trials with and without sleepers. Second,
347 data for left target locations were flipped on data for right target locations (after recentering both to
348 correct for the bivariate Gaussian variation). Mean response coordinates are shown in Figure 3 for
349 each of the four target locations separately for Same Side, Opposite, and No Wall conditions with
350 ellipses capturing about 80% of the responses (a figure showing left and right data separately is
351 provided in the supplementary materials). As visible, bias in pointing responses revealed the more
352 underestimation of distances the more distant target locations were. Furthermore, an inward bias was
353 apparent for the more lateral target locations 1 (L1/R1) and 4 (L4/R4). Precision was higher for these
354 lateral target locations with a lateral wall on the Same Side as indicated by smaller ellipses.

355 To quantify bias on the x- and y-axes as well as precision at each level of the lateral wall
356 manipulation, Bayesian estimation was applied for modeling pointing responses separately for each
357 target location as bivariate normally distributed and grouped by a nominal predictor. For x- and y-
358 coordinates, intercepts and group deflections were estimated together with group-specific covariance
359 matrices, from which the rotation angle θ of data ellipses could be computed. Intercepts are denoted
360 β_{x0} and β_{y0} , respectively. Group deflections are denoted $\beta_x[i]$ and $\beta_y[i]$ with i varying from 1 to 3 for
361 the levels of the lateral wall manipulation. Both $\beta_x[i]$ and $\beta_y[i]$ sum to zero.

362 Bayesian estimation was implemented in R and JAGS (Plummer, 2003) by combining and adapting a
363 script for a single normally distributed variable with one nominal predictor provided in Kruschke
364 (2015) and a script for estimating parameters of a bivariate normal distribution provided by Bååth
365 (2013) following their recommendations for non-committal priors. The R script and data files for
366 replicating the analysis are provided in the OSF.

367 The modes and the lower and upper boundaries of 95% highest density intervals of posterior
368 distributions of parameter estimates are shown in Table 2 for the intercepts β_{x0} and β_{y0} and rotation
369 angles. Figure 4 shows modes and 95% HDI boundaries for the group deflections $\beta_x[i]$ and $\beta_y[i]$ and
370 standard deviations $\sigma_x[i]$ and $\sigma_y[i]$. Underestimation of distances on the forward axis increasing with
371 the distance of target locations is confirmed in increasingly negative values of β_{y0} from target
372 location 4 to target location 1 with non-overlapping HDIs (Table 2). The bias in the x-direction
373 reflected in β_{x0} was inward (negative signed error) for the more lateral target locations 1 and 4 and
374 close to zero for target locations 2 and 3. A lateral wall on the same side pushed responses for the
375 lateral target locations 1 and 4 even slightly more inward as shown by negative β_x for Same Side in
376 Figure 4. In contrast, responses for target locations 2 and 3 seemed to be pulled slightly outward as
377 indicated by positive β_x for Same Side.

378 Response precision has been estimated by the standard deviations shown in Figure 5. Lower standard
379 deviations on the forward axis σ_y corresponding to higher precision were observed for the lateral
380 target locations 1 and 4 when a lateral wall was on the Same Side, most clearly for the closer target
381 location 4. Standard deviations in the x-direction did not show consistent effects of the lateral wall
382 manipulation, but were also slightly decreased for the lateral target locations 1 and 4 in the Same
383 Side condition.

384 The estimates for the rotation angle of the response point clouds (Table 2) turned out higher with a
385 lateral wall on the Same Side for all but the most distant target location 1 (consistent with a stronger
386 inward bias for less distant locations). For target locations 2 and 4, the Same Side HDIs for θ are
387 clearly above and non-overlapping with the HDIs for Opposite and No Wall, which are highly
388 overlapping for all target locations.

389 **3.3 Discussion**

390 The overall analysis of absolute distance error did not reveal reliable effects of the sleepers (optic
391 flow) manipulation and the spatial reference provided by a lateral wall with distinctive features as
392 landmarks. However, slight trends were consistent with the presumed updating-supporting effects of
393 increased optic flow and spatial reference. Effects of spatial reference showed up for target locations
394 close to the lateral wall. Bayesian estimation of signed error on the x- and y- (forward) axes allowed
395 to quantify bias and precision at different levels of the spatial reference manipulation separately for
396 the four target locations (not assuming variance homogeneity as in standard ANOVAs). The results
397 confirmed the well-known phenomenon of distance underestimation in VR (Renner et al., 2013;
398 Vienne et al., 2020), which increased with target distance (evident in y- and x-intercepts). In addition,
399 results showed clearly that effects of the spatial reference manipulation were restricted to the two
400 target locations close to the lateral wall: the target location 1 furthest from the participant and the
401 target location 4 closest to the participant. The lateral wall increased precision of the pointing
402 responses particularly by reducing variance on the y-axis and pushed pointing responses slightly
403 inward only for the two target locations close to the lateral wall. The inward bias is consistent with
404 previous results of Negen et al. (2020), who also found that target locations were reproduced with a
405 bias inward away from close boundaries.

406 It is possible, that the optic flow manipulation had turned out more influential if all other visual cues
407 potentially processed for updating would have been minimized. This is suggested by the small and
408 unreliable Sleepers effect without any wall. The lateral wall if present did not only provide static
409 reference but also increased optic flow and thus may have diminished the Sleepers effect. We did not
410 study optic flow without persisting visual cues (e.g., by flaring random dots or fiery textures) because
411 our interest in effective support for spatial updating in VR is motivated partly by such support's
412 relevance in applied contexts such as teleoperation of vehicles and mobile robots and there, very
413 sparse environments are uncommon. Environments typically contain boundaries and landmarks or at
414 least, they could be added in VR or added by augmented reality techniques to immersive
415 teleoperation interfaces (Suzuki et al., 2022). Hence, we strengthened support and investigated
416 effects of boundaries and landmarks separately and in combination in Experiment 2 along with
417 idiothetic cues from real walking. Landmarks were placed inside the boundary close to target
418 locations.

419 **4 Experiment 2 – Landmarks and boundaries with translation and walking**

420 Again, participants encoded two target locations, one of which had to be reproduced after forward
421 self-motion. We varied whether only a boundary was available as spatial context, or instead five
422 objects as close landmarks, or both a boundary and the five landmarks within the boundary. We
423 expected that support in reproducing target locations and effects showing up in bias and precision
424 should be stronger for target locations close to the boundary and/or landmarks as indicated in
425 Experiment 1 and suggested by multiple previous studies (McNamara, 2013). When both boundary
426 and landmarks are present, cue combination may produce particularly strong support as well as bias
427 and precision effects (Newman & McNamara, 2022). In previous studies (e.g., Kelly et al., 2008),

428 boundary shapes have been selected to vary the presence and alignment of main axes, and the
429 presence of vertices that could function as landmarks similar to objects (among other factors, e.g.,
430 rotational symmetry, which is relevant if self-motion encompasses rotation). The participants
431 experienced one of three boundary shapes: a rectangle with two lateral walls aligned with forward
432 translation, a trapezoid with lateral walls oblique to forward translation, and an ellipse with the
433 longer axis aligned with forward translation. All three shapes had a main axis aligned with forward
434 translation, but only the rectangle and the trapezoid contained vertices as potential landmarks. Target
435 locations were placed in between boundary and landmarks (thus being enclosed if both were present),
436 and one was placed between landmarks to which it was closer than to the boundary. Enclosing could
437 amplify the benefit of cue combination.

438 In addition to varying available spatial context and the placement of target locations, we let
439 participants experience real walking instead of passive forward translation in half of the trials.
440 Idiothetic cues from real walking were effective support for spatial updating in previous studies if
441 self-motion included rotation (Klatzky et al., 1998; Kearns et al., 2002; Ruddle & Lessels, 2006;
442 Wraga et al., 2004) and in a subset of studies also for forward translation (Chance et al., 1998). To
443 test potential supporting effects of real walking on forward updating of location memory in the
444 context of boundaries and/or landmarks, we compared passive translation with real walking in
445 Experiment 2.

446 **4.1 Materials and methods**

447 **4.1.1 Participants**

448 Thirty-six students of Chemnitz University of Technology (16 men, 20 women) with a mean age of
449 25.94 years ($SD = 4.87$) participated in a single session that lasted around 180 min in partial
450 fulfilment of a curricular requirement or for monetary compensation (10 EUR/h). Nine additional
451 participants were replaced: One participant did not complete the study due to technical failure, two
452 participants deviated often from the correct path in walking trials, and data of six participants had to
453 be excluded due to technical error in presenting the pointing task.

454 **4.1.2 Design**

455 The experiment constituted a 3 x 3 x 2 mixed factorial design including boundary shape (Rectangle,
456 Trapezoid, Ellipse) as a between-subjects factor, and environment (Landmarks, Boundary, Boundary
457 and Landmarks) and translation type (passive Translation, real Walking) as within-subjects factors.

458 **4.1.3 Apparatus and stimuli**

459 As in Experiment 1, the virtual environment was a light-ochre floor plane under a cloudless blue sky
460 (Figure 6). When only landmarks were presented, the floor plane extended to the horizon. Landmarks
461 were a pair of soccer balls (20 cm high) spaced 7 m apart, a pair of plants (80 cm) spaced 4.2 m apart,
462 and a chair (80 cm) tiered in front of the participant. Measured from the starting location of the
463 participant at coordinates (0, 0) on the left-right and front-back axes, respectively, the chair was 21 m
464 ahead. Boundaries were walls of 3 m height and enclosed the starting location and all landmark
465 locations. The boundary shape was either a 15 m by 24 m rectangle, an isosceles trapezoid whose
466 width extended from 15 m to 34.35 m over a height of 25 m, or a 21.22 m by 31.80 m ellipse. The
467 starting location in the rectangle was 1.5 m apart from the wall opposite to the chair location. The
468 trapezoid and the ellipse were constructed such that the part of the rectangle ahead of the starting
469 location fitted inside as shown in Figure 7.

470 Target coordinates were drawn from bivariate Gaussian distributions ($SD = 1$ m) centered at four
471 locations to the left and four mirrored locations to the right of the forward axis per boundary shape
472 (Table 3). The target locations were chosen to be located either near at a distance of 9 m (locations 1
473 and 4) or far at 12.5 m (locations 2 and 3) from the participant's location at (0, 7) after 7 m forward
474 translation. Furthermore, distances to landmarks and boundaries were considered. Target location 2
475 was 1.5 m away from the plant landmark and thus the closest to a landmark. Target location 3 was
476 1.5 m away from the boundary (with different coordinates for the rectangle than for trapezoid and
477 ellipse). Target location 4 was close to the boundary (1.5 m) only for the rectangle. All target
478 locations were enclosed between landmarks (1) or between boundary and landmarks (2, 3, and 4). As
479 in Experiment 1, two red cross shapes were presented as left and right target objects in each trial with
480 non-symmetric target locations. The starting location was marked by a small red X-mark at the center
481 of a white circle with a diameter of 3 m.

482 Translation was either passive translation or real walking for 5, 6, or 7m. Participants again
483 responded with the controller by placing a wireframe model shown where a laser beam intersected
484 with the floor plane. An arrow on the laser beam indicated the side, for which the target object
485 location was to be reproduced.

486 **4.1.4 Procedure**

487 After being informed about the procedure of the experiment and the tasks to be performed, the
488 participant signed informed consent and was instructed by the experimenter how to put on and adjust
489 the head-mounted display and how to operate the controller. Then, the participant worked through 18
490 training trials experiencing three trials each for passive translation and then real walking first within
491 the respective boundary, second with landmarks only, and then for boundary and landmarks
492 combined. Different target locations than in experimental trials were used and feedback was provided
493 as in the first half of training trials in Experiment 1. No feedback was provided in experimental trials.

494 The participant stood upright at the starting location and initiated a trial with the trigger button on the
495 controller. A left and a right target object were presented and sank into the ground. Passive
496 translation trials proceeded as in Experiment 1 with a translation interval of 2.8 to 3.1 s. Subsequent
497 to the response, the participant was passively turned and translated back to the starting location. In
498 real walking trials, the onset of a melody right after the target objects had disappeared prompted the
499 participant to start and keep walking forward until a gong sound stopped walking. When lateral
500 deviation exceeded 0.3 m, the melody was replaced by noise until walking was back on track. At the
501 onset of the gong sound that stopped walking, the response interval started. After the response, a sign
502 popped up for 2 s instructing the participant to "Please, turn around and go back". When the
503 participant reached the starting location in the white circle, a second sign popped up for 2 s
504 instructing to "Please, turn around and proceed".

505 Participants worked through six blocks of trials. Each block consisted of 24 trials for a particular
506 combination of environment and translation type (e.g., Landmarks and Translation) and included one
507 trial for each target location to-be-reproduced left and right with each translation distance (4 x 2 x 3).
508 This resulted in a total of 144 experimental trials. The sequence of blocks was balanced according to
509 a Latin square. The order of trials within a block was pseudorandomized ensuring that target
510 locations were distributed evenly across the trial sequence, translation distances did not repeat more
511 than once in subsequent trials, and that no more than two subsequent to-be-reproduced target
512 locations were on the same side. Participants took a brief break after each block.

513 **4.2 Results**

514 Again, trials were retained for analysis if responses were to the correct side, pointing error was not
515 higher than 6m of absolute Euclidean distance from the target location, and response time was less
516 than 8 s (98% of all trials). In repeated-measures ANOVAs, *F*-values have been Greenhouse-Geisser
517 corrected where necessary.

518 **4.2.1 Absolute distance error**

519 Mean absolute distance error is shown in Figure 8 separately for the three boundary groups. The type
520 of self-motion had no consistent effect. In particular, error in real walking trials was not consistently
521 lower than in passive translation trials. In the ellipse group, even the opposite trend was apparent
522 across environment conditions. With both types of self-motion and in all three groups, mean error
523 was higher in the Boundary condition than in the Landmarks and Boundary-and-Landmarks
524 conditions. Note, that in comparing performance across the groups, it has to be kept in mind that
525 target location 3 was located more inward in the Rectangle than in the Trapezoid and Ellipse groups.

526 Repeated-measures ANOVAs including the factors type of self-motion and environment were
527 computed separately for the three boundary groups. In the Rectangle group, there was no reliable
528 main effect of self-motion type, $F(1, 11) = 1.20, p = .30, \eta_p^2 = .10$, the main effect of environment
529 was confirmed, $F(2, 22) = 8.85, p = .009, \eta_p^2 = .45$, and there was no reliable interaction, $F(2, 22) =$
530 $0.76, p = .43, \eta_p^2 = .06$. In the Trapezoid group, the pattern of effects was similar: no reliable main
531 effect of self-motion type, $F(1, 11) = 0.59, p = .46, \eta_p^2 = .05$, a clear main effect of environment, $F(2,$
532 $22) = 9.69, p = .007, \eta_p^2 = .47$, and no reliable interaction, $F(2, 22) = 0.54, p = .52, \eta_p^2 = .05$. In the
533 Ellipse group, the unexpected advantage of translation over walking was confirmed by a main effect
534 of self-motion type, $F(1, 11) = 8.55, p = .014, \eta_p^2 = .44$. The main effect of environment was again
535 reliable, $F(2, 22) = 17.55, p = .001, \eta_p^2 = .62$, and again there was no indication of an interaction, $F(2,$
536 $22) = 0.23, p = .68, \eta_p^2 = .02$.

537 In all three boundary groups, mean absolute distance error was higher in the Boundary condition than
538 in the Landmarks and Boundary-and-Landmarks conditions with $d = 0.88, 0.84$, and 1.43 , and $d =$
539 $0.61, 1.06$, and 1.65 for the Rectangle, Trapezoid, and Ellipse groups, respectively. In the Rectangle
540 group, distance error was similar in the Boundary-and-Landmarks and the Landmarks conditions,
541 paired t-test $t(11) = 0.67, p = .52, d = 0.17$, whereas in the Trapezoid and Ellipse groups, error was
542 slightly lower in the Boundary-and-Landmarks condition with $t(11) = -2.06, p = .06, d = -0.65$, and
543 $t(11) = -1.72, p = .11, d = -0.30$, respectively.

544 **4.2.2 Bias and precision**

545 For the subsequent analyses of bias and precision, data for both self-motion types have been
546 combined, because the effects of self-motion type were inconsistent and small compared to the
547 consistent and strong environment effect. As for the Bayesian analyses of Experiment 1, data for left
548 target locations were flipped on data for right target locations (after recentering both to correct for the
549 bivariate Gaussian variation). Mean response coordinates are shown in Figures 9 (Rectangle), 10
550 (Trapezoid), and 11 (Ellipse) for each of the four target locations separately for Landmarks,
551 Boundary, and Boundary-and-Landmarks with ellipses capturing about 80% of the responses (figures
552 showing left and right data separately are provided in the supplementary materials).

553 General patterns visible in the Figures are, first, that responses are pushed away from close
554 boundaries, second, that the presence of landmarks (in the chosen placement of targets, landmarks,
555 and boundaries) reduced distance error and increased precision more than the presence of boundaries,
556 and third, that typically, the presence of both boundary and landmarks resulted in the highest

557 precision. For target location 1 that was enclosed between landmarks and most distant from the
558 boundary, the presence of a boundary in addition to landmarks, did hardly increase precision further.

559 As for Experiment 1, Bayesian estimation was applied to quantify effects of the presence of a
560 boundary and/or landmarks on bias and precision. The modes and the lower and upper boundaries of
561 95% highest density intervals of posterior distributions of parameter estimates are shown in Tables 4
562 to 6 for the intercepts β_{x0} and β_{y0} and rotation angles for the boundary groups Rectangle, Trapezoid,
563 and Ellipse, respectively. Figures 12 and 13 show modes and 95% HDI boundaries for the deflections
564 created by Landmarks, Boundary, and Boundary-and-Landmarks $\beta_x[i]$ and $\beta_y[i]$ and standard
565 deviations $\sigma_x[i]$ and $\sigma_y[i]$, respectively.

566 Higher underestimation of distances on the forward axis with increasing distance of target locations
567 is indicated by more negative estimates for β_{y0} for the more distant target locations 2 and 3 than for
568 target locations 1 and 4, for instance -0.92 and -0.74 vs. -0.63 and -0.46, respectively, for the
569 Rectangle group (Table 4, and similarly for Trapezoid and Ellipse in Tables 5 and 6). The inward
570 bias indicated by more negative values of β_{x0} was most pronounced for the most lateral target
571 location 3 and in the Rectangle group also for the equally lateral target location 4 (Tables 4 to 6).

572 The presence of a boundary without landmarks resulted in a relative inward bias as indicated by
573 negative deflections β_x (Figure 12) particularly for target locations closer to the boundary (not for
574 target location 1), in contrast, the presence of landmarks without a boundary in the chosen
575 configuration resulted in a reduced inward bias and thus a relative outward bias as indicated by
576 positive deflections β_x (not for target location 1). On the forward axis, the presence of a boundary
577 without landmarks resulted in a relatively strong distance underestimation as indicated by negative
578 deflections β_y particularly for target location 4 closest to the participant on the forward axis. In
579 contrast, the presence of landmarks in the chosen configuration reduced underestimation of distance
580 on the forward axis (not for target location 1).

581 Most clearly for precision on the forward axis as indicated by low standard deviations σ_y in Figure
582 13, Landmarks increased precision in the chosen configuration compared to Boundary only and the
583 combination of Boundary-and-Landmarks increased precision further only slightly if at all. For
584 precision on the x-axis, the differences between environment conditions were less pronounced and
585 less consistent across target locations, however, increased precision with the combination of
586 Boundary-and-Landmarks compared to Landmarks or Boundary only was observed for target
587 locations 3 and 4.

588 Rotation angles θ in Tables 4 to 6 reflect an alignment of response distributions with lateral
589 boundaries particularly for target location 4 with lower rotation angles for Boundary than Landmarks.
590 The same difference is apparent in rotation angles for target location 3 in the Trapezoid and Ellipse
591 groups.

592 4.3 Discussion

593 Landmarks alone and in combination with a boundary did reduce absolute distance error in
594 reproducing locations compared to the Boundary condition. However, real walking that provided
595 idiothetic in addition to visual cues to self-motion did not reduce distance error compared to passive
596 translation. Either idiothetic cues provide no advantage in spatial updating across forward self-
597 motion for target locations that remain in vista space or visual cues provided by spatial context took
598 primacy in the present experiment. It is possible that an effect of idiothetic cues could be shown if

599 static visual reference would be eliminated (e.g., by showing only flaring random dots as floor
600 texture as in Wolbers et al., 2008). Yet, some static visual reference is typically available in VR and
601 teleoperation scenarios.

602 Landmarks were located inside the boundary and the rectangle and trapezoid boundaries contained
603 vertices that could function as landmarks. In addition to the absence of vertices, the area inside the
604 boundary stretched further ahead for the ellipse whereas it was limited by a wall perpendicular to the
605 forward axis for rectangle and trapezoid. Vertices and the limited stretch presumably are the reasons
606 why in the boundary-only condition, distance error was smaller for rectangle and trapezoid than for
607 the ellipse. Such an advantage of the rectangle and trapezoid groups could also explain smaller
608 distance error than in the ellipse group in the landmarks only condition with the additional
609 assumption that the (imagined) wall ahead took effect even in trials in which it was not shown. An
610 alternative explanation would be that average performance of participants in the ellipse group was
611 lower because of interindividual differences. As in Experiment 1, the general underestimation of
612 distances in VR was replicated again, but landmarks reduced distance underestimation.

613 The presence of landmarks inside the boundary reduced distance error by reducing bias and
614 increasing precision. The boundary pushed responses inside for targets close to the boundary
615 consistent with similar results in Negen et al. (2020) and landmarks when present counteracted this
616 bias. For locations enclosed between a boundary and an inside landmark, cue combination increased
617 precision. For location 1 that was enclosed between inside landmarks but more distant from the
618 boundary, cue combination seems restricted to the two landmarks because the additional presence of
619 a boundary did not increase precision further.

620 The orientation of walls mattered. In the Boundary condition, the response distributions were more
621 aligned with the lateral boundary. Laterally, the boundaries were closer to lateral target locations than
622 in Experiment 1, however, there were no inside landmarks in Experiment 1 and hence, we cannot be
623 sure that this alignment with a lateral boundary would be as strong if a comparison condition
624 contained no inside landmarks.

625 In summary, we succeeded in supporting forward updating by landmarks inside boundaries and
626 demonstrated benefits of a boundary wall perpendicular to the motion direction as well as of static
627 visual cues enclosing target locations (decreased bias and increased precision). Visual cues took
628 primacy over idiothetic cues for pure forward updating in vista space in immersive VR.

629 **5 General discussion**

630 We were interested in factors contributing to spatial updating of location memory across forward
631 self-motion in VR. Increased optic flow (overhead sleepers during translation) provided no clear
632 advantage with passive forward translation in Experiment 1 and no advantage was obtained for real
633 walking compared to passive translation in Experiment 2. The missing advantage for real walking
634 and the small Sleepers effect even without any wall are consistent with the presumption that very
635 little dynamic visual stimulation aka optic flow is sufficient for continuous forward updating and
636 thus, passive forward translation experienced in an MRI scanner may generate brain activation
637 similar to real translation scenarios (e.g., Wolbers et al., 2008). Yet, to be sure that idiothetic cues
638 provide no advantage for forward updating as soon as minimal optic flow is provided, passive
639 translation would need to be compared with real walking in minimal optic flow conditions (e.g.,
640 flaring random dots).

641 The richness of spatial context and proximity of landmarks to targets improved updating. We found
642 supporting effects of static visual cues in both experiments. A lateral boundary with distinctive
643 features when close (Experiment 1), a boundary perpendicular to the forward axis (Experiment 2),
644 and especially close landmarks inside boundaries (Experiment 2) reduced biases and increased
645 precision in reproducing target locations. The combined effect of landmarks and boundaries (cue
646 combination, Newman & McNamara, 2022) was particularly strong if targets were enclosed between
647 landmarks and boundaries. Thus, for forward updating in vista space in immersive VR, close visual
648 spatial reference seems to be the most promising means of support.

649 If self-motion would have entailed rotation of more than say 90 degrees, real walking may well have
650 provided support by idiothetic cues to self-motion (e.g., Gramann et al., 2021) because then, changes
651 in head direction need to be accounted for in updating mechanisms as specified in current
652 neuroscientific theories (Byrne et al., 2007; Bicanski & Burgess, 2018). However, effects of real
653 walking with rotation are presumably stronger in sparse spatial context or may even be restricted to
654 sparse spatial context (Riecke et al., 2007). The present results let us expect that close visual cues as
655 spatial reference would take primacy over idiothetic cues even with rotation. Boundary shapes and
656 corners as boundary features had smaller effects than inside landmarks in the present experiments. If
657 self-motion entails rotation, however, features of boundary shapes become important that can provide
658 cues to orientation in the environment, for instance, those with corners as opposed to no corners, or
659 lower as opposed to higher degrees of rotational symmetry (e.g., trapezoid vs. circle). Similarly,
660 distant landmarks beyond the boundary are important orientation cues across extensive rotation
661 which can be added as AR support to an egocentric view (e.g., Liu et al., 2022).

662 Restricting self-motion to forward translation or forward walking allowed to reliably determine
663 biases in the x- and y-directions in reproducing locations and how these biases were influenced by
664 boundaries and landmarks, more reliably than would have been possible if participants had
665 experienced variable rotation across trials. Presumably, participants worked with both egocentric and
666 allocentric spatial representations including egocentric representations in the fronto-parietal network
667 underlying spatial working memory (Curtis, 2006; Kesner & Creem-Regehr, 2013) and spatial
668 representations (allocentric and egocentric) in parahippocampal and hippocampal cortex (Byrne et
669 al., 2007; Bicanski & Burgess, 2018). Only requiring forward updating in vista space kept egocentric
670 and allocentric frames aligned and did not pose the challenge of transforming between allocentric and
671 egocentric representations (which reliably involves retrosplenial cortex; Gramann et al., 2021). It is
672 noteworthy that according to recent findings employing single-cell recording in humans (Kunz et al.,
673 2021), continuous updating of egocentric representations in parahippocampal cortex across self-
674 motion that included rotation (inferred from firing rates of egocentric bearing cells) occurred based
675 on purely visual information in non-immersive VR (laptop screen). Thus, our results suggesting
676 visual primacy obtained with an HMD may generalize to less immersive VR with scenes that provide
677 at least some static visual reference. Static visual spatial reference if available seems to dominate
678 visual and idiothetic dynamic cues for updating location memory even though in immersive VR optic
679 flow stimulates over a large field of view. However, static and dynamic visual cues have not been
680 discerned in the present paradigm. Optic flow is also available in sparse environments and even more
681 so if static visual cues are present. Thus, any static visual cues also contribute to dynamic visual cues
682 to updating.

683 For supporting location memory in VR, close (inside) landmarks as spatial reference have proven
684 more effective than boundaries. This may also be true for supporting spatial updating for orientation
685 and navigation in VR as assessed by triangle completion. It is straightforward to include rotation in
686 experienced self-motion and to test the effect of close landmarks on reproducing locations or triangle

687 completion (reproducing the starting location) as in Sjolund et al. (2018), for example. Another
688 interesting follow-up to the present experiments would be to employ conditions introducing
689 inconsistencies between boundary and landmarks, for instance, rotating the landmark configuration
690 inside the boundary between encoding and reproducing locations or during the outward path in
691 triangle completion. Such manipulations allow to study the weighing of cues in cue combination and
692 whether available cues are combined optimally given their reliabilities. Cue combination of visual
693 and idiothetic cues has been studied before for triangle completion in sparse environments (e.g.,
694 Chen et al., 2017; Sjolund et al., 2018).

695 The scenes in Experiment 1 were sparse and the shape of the lateral wall changed from trial to trial
696 while the forward pair of poles remained the same. The participant perspective was abruptly reset to
697 the starting location after translation trials. In contrast, in Experiment 2, the scene remained
698 unchanged within a block of trials and the participant perspective changed continuously. Thus, in
699 Experiment 2 conditions were more favorable for establishing a scene representation, however, we
700 presume that the constancy of the geometric layout across trials in Experiment 1 also induced the
701 experience of a single scene or at least of scenes with a constant layout. In Experiment 2, the
702 landmark conditions were equivalent across the boundary groups, still, there was a slight advantage
703 of the rectangle and trapezoid groups in landmark conditions. Hence, if the ellipse group was not a
704 group containing individuals performing generally lower, this advantage can be explained by carry-
705 over effects from earlier blocks with boundaries. Participants may have imagined the boundary that
706 they had experienced in trials with a boundary in later landmark trials.

707 The landmark objects in Experiment 2 were placed to indicate the forward direction (chair) and to
708 provide spatial reference in variable distance to target locations (plant, ball). Landmarks to the left
709 had symmetric counterparts to the right. Thus, the landmarks formed a regular configuration, a
710 polygon symmetric at the forward axis. The lines connecting symmetric landmarks were
711 perpendicular to the forward axis. In Experiment 2, targets were never located on these lines, but if
712 they had been, bias on the y-axis probably had been reduced to almost zero for these trials. Similarly,
713 strong support by spatial reference can be expected for other salient locations in landmark
714 configurations (e.g., the center). Furthermore, configurations as boundary shapes can entail
715 prominent axes that contribute allocentric reference. Effects of such allocentric reference (supporting
716 and distorting) have been studied extensively in research on spatial memory (e.g., Zhou & Mou,
717 2019; Shelton & McNamara, 2001). Hence, if local landmarks are added to scenes to support spatial
718 memory, orientation, and navigation, the effects of configurations of landmarks (Newman &
719 McNamara, 2022) and of configurations with boundary features can be considered for amplifying
720 their utility.

721 In the present study, we have demonstrated the primacy of static visual cues in spatial updating
722 across forward translation in immersive VR for reproducing target locations in vista space by
723 quantifying in detail reductions in bias and increases in precision. Landmarks combined with
724 boundaries provide spatial context that according to behavioral and neuroscientific evidence provides
725 a reference frame that is used to establish egocentric and allocentric spatial representations.
726 Allocentric representations contain the ego-location in the present scene and are employed in
727 updating egocentric representations. We studied close landmarks inside boundaries and based on our
728 results suggest to strongly consider providing not only distant (Liu et al., 2022) but also close
729 landmarks in virtual environments and as augmented reality features (Suzuki et al., 2022) in synthetic
730 environments (e.g., in teleoperation) for alleviating challenges to spatial orientation resulting from
731 reduced sensory feedback about self-motion.

732 **6 Data availability statement**

733 The datasets and scripts for replicating the analyses are openly available at the project's Open
734 Science Framework page: <https://osf.io/e39jf/>.

735 **7 Ethics statement**

736 All procedures were determined by the applicable body (Ethics committee of the Faculty of
737 Behavioral and Social Sciences of Chemnitz University of Technology) not to require in-depth ethics
738 evaluation (V-332-15-GJ-Telepresence-13052019).

739 **8 Author contributions**

740 All authors contributed to conception and design of the experiments. SW set up the experiments in
741 Unity, ZB and JB conducted the experiments, ZB and GJ performed the statistical analyses and wrote
742 sections of the manuscript, all authors read and approved the submitted version.

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746 **10 Acknowledgments**

747 [thanks to reviewers]

748 **11 Conflict of interest**

749 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
750 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

751 **12 References**

752 Attneave, F., and Farrar, P. (1977). The visual world behind the head. *Am. J. Psychol.* 90, 549-563.
753 doi: 10.2307/1421729

754 Bååth, R. (2013). The Bayesian counterpart of Pearson's correlation test. *Publishable Stuff: Rasmus*
755 *Bååth's Research Blog*. <https://www.sumsar.net/blog/2013/08/bayesian-estimation-of-correlation/>
756 [Accessed January 15, 2023].

757 Barhorst-Cates, E. M., Stoker, J., Stefanucci, J. K., and Creem-Regehr, S. H. (2021). Using virtual
758 reality to assess dynamic self-motion and landmark cues for spatial updating in children and adults.
759 *Mem. Cognition* 49, 572–585. doi: 10.3758/s13421-020-01111-8

760 Bicanski, A., and Burgess, N. (2018). A neural-level model of spatial memory and imagery. *Elife*
761 7:e33752. doi: 10.7554/eLife.33752

762 Buckley, M. G., Austen, J. M., Myles, L. A., Smith, S., Ihssen, N., Lew, A. R., and McGregor, A.
763 (2021). The effects of spatial stability and cue type on spatial learning: Implications for theories of
764 parallel memory systems. *Cognition* 214:104802. doi: 10.1016/j.cognition.2021.104802

- 765 Byrne, P., Becker, S., and Burgess, N. (2007). Remembering the past and imagining the future: A
766 neural model of spatial memory and imagery. *Psychol. Rev.* 114, 340-375. doi: 10.1037/0033-
767 295X.114.2.340
- 768 Chance, S. S., Gaunet, F., Beall, A. C., and Loomis, J. M. (1998). Locomotion mode affects the
769 updating of objects encountered during travel: The contribution of vestibular and proprioceptive
770 inputs to path integration. *Presence* 7, 168-178. doi: 10.1162/105474698565659
- 771 Chen, X., McNamara, T. P., Kelly, J. W., and Wolbers, T. (2017). Cue combination in human spatial
772 navigation. *Cognitive Psychol.* 95, 105-144. doi: 10.1016/j.cogpsych.2017.04.003
- 773 Cheng, K., Shettleworth, S. J., Huttenlocher, J., and Rieser, J. J. (2007). Bayesian integration of
774 spatial information. *Psychol. Bull.* 133, 625–637. doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.133.4.625
- 775 Cherep, L. A., Lim, A. F., Kelly, J. W., Acharya, D., Velasco, A., Bustamante, E., Ostrander, A. G.,
776 and Gilbert, S. B. (2020). Spatial cognitive implications of teleporting through virtual environments.
777 *J. Exp. Psychol.-Appl.* 26, 480–492. doi: 10.1037/xap0000263
- 778 Chrastil, E. R., and Warren, W. H. (2012). Active and passive contributions to spatial learning.
779 *Psychon. B. Rev.* 19, 1-23. doi: 10.3758/s13423-011-0182-x
- 780 Curtis, C. E. (2006). Prefrontal and parietal contributions to spatial working memory. *Neuroscience*
781 139, 173–180. doi: 10.1016/J.Neuroscience.2005.04.070
- 782 Doeller, C. F., and Burgess, N. (2008). Distinct error-correcting and incidental learning of location
783 relative to landmarks and boundaries. *P. Natl. A. Sci.* 105, 5909-5914. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0711433105
- 784 Ekstrom, A. D., Spiers, H. J., Bohbot, V. D., and Rosenbaum, R. S. (2018). *Human Spatial*
785 *Navigation*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- 786 Evans, T., Bicanski, A., Bush, D., and Burgess, N. (2016). How environment and self-motion
787 combine in neural representations of space. *J. Physiol.* 594, 6535-6546. doi: 10.1113/JP270666
- 788 Gallistel, C. R. (1990). *The Organization of Learning*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- 789 Gramann, K., Hohlefeld, F. U., Gehrke, L., and Klug, M. (2021). Human cortical dynamics during
790 full-body heading changes. *Sci. Rep.- UK* 11:18186. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-97749-8
- 791 Hodgson, E., and Waller, D. (2006). Lack of set size effects in spatial updating: Evidence for offline
792 updating. *J. Exp. Psychol. Learn.* 32, 854–866. doi: 10.1037/0278-7393.32.4.854
- 793 Jeffery, K. J., and O’Keefe, J. M. (1999). Learned interaction of visual and idiothetic cues in the
794 control of place field orientation. *Exp. Brain Res.* 127, 151-161. doi: 10.1007/s002210050785
- 795 Kearns, M. J., Warren, W. H., Duchon, A. P., and Tarr, M. J. (2002). Path integration from optic flow
796 and body senses in a homing task. *Perception* 31, 349-374. doi: 10.1068/p3311
- 797 Kelly, J., Doty, T., Cherep, L., and Gilbert, S. B. (2022). Boundaries reduce disorientation in virtual
798 reality. *Front. Virtual Real.* 3:882526. doi: 10.3389/frvir.2022.882526

- 799 Kelly, J. W., McNamara, T. P., Bodenheimer, B., Carr, T. H., and Rieser, J. J. (2008). The shape of
800 human navigation: How environmental geometry is used in maintenance of spatial orientation.
801 *Cognition* 109, 281-286. doi: 10.1016/j.cognition.2008.09.001
- 802 Kelly, J. W., Sjolund, L. A., and Sturz, B. R. (2013). Geometric cues, reference frames, and the
803 equivalence of experienced-aligned and novel-aligned views in human spatial memory. *Cognition*
804 126, 459-474. doi: 10.1016/j.cognition.2012.11.007
- 805 Klatzky, R. L., Loomis, J. M., Beall, A. C., Chance, S. S., and Golledge, R. G. (1998). Spatial
806 updating of self-position and orientation during real, imagined, and virtual locomotion. *Psychol. Sci.*
807 9, 293-298. doi: 10.1111/1467-9280.00058
- 808 Kruschke, J. K. (2015). *Doing Bayesian Data Analysis: A Tutorial with R, JAGS, and Stan*. 2nd Edn.
809 Academic Press.
- 810 Kunz, L., Brandt, A., Reinacher, P. C., Staresina, B. P., Reifensstein, E. T., Weidemann, C. T., et al.
811 (2021). A neural code for egocentric spatial maps in the human medial temporal lobe. *Neuron* 109,
812 2781-2796. doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2021.06.019
- 813 Liu, J., Singh, A. K., Wunderlich, A., Gramann, K., and Lin, C. T. (2022). Redesigning navigational
814 aids using virtual global landmarks to improve spatial knowledge retrieval. *Sci. Learn.* 7:17. doi:
815 10.1038/s41539-022-00132-z
- 816 Loomis, J. M., Klatzky, R. L., Golledge, R. G., Cicinelli, J. G., Pellegrino, J. W., and Fry, P. A.
817 (1993). Nonvisual navigation by blind and sighted: Assessment of path integration ability. *J. Exp.*
818 *Psychol. Gen.* 122, 73-91. doi: 10.1037/0096-3445.122.1.73
- 819 McNamara, T. P. (2013). "Spatial memory: Properties and organization," in *Handbook of Spatial*
820 *Cognition*, ed. D. Waller and L. Nadel (Washington, DC: American Psychological Association),
821 173–190. doi: 10.1037/13936-010
- 822 Mou, W., McNamara, T. P., Valiquette, C. M., and Rump, B. (2004). Allocentric and egocentric
823 updating of spatial memories. *J. Exp. Psychol. Learn.* 30, 142-157. doi: 10.1037/0278-7393.30.1.142
- 824 Negen, J., Sandri, A., Lee, S. A., and Nardini, M. (2020). Boundaries in spatial cognition: Looking
825 like a boundary is more important than being a boundary. *J. Exp. Psychol. Learn.* 46, 1007–1021.
826 doi: 10.1037/xlm0000760
- 827 Newman, P. M., and McNamara, T. P. (2022). Integration of visual landmark cues in spatial memory.
828 *Psychol. Res. - Psych.Fo.* 86, 1636–1654. doi: 10.1007/s00426-021-01581-8
- 829 Plummer, M. (2003). "JAGS: A program for analysis of Bayesian graphical models using Gibbs
830 sampling," in *Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Distributed Statistical Computing*
831 *(DSC 2003)*, ed. K. Hornik, F. Leisch, and A. Zeileis. [https://www.r-project.org/conferences/DSC-](https://www.r-project.org/conferences/DSC-2003/Proceedings/Plummer.pdf)
832 [2003/Proceedings/Plummer.pdf](https://www.r-project.org/conferences/DSC-2003/Proceedings/Plummer.pdf)
- 833 Presson, C. C., and Montello, D. R. (1994). Updating after rotational and translational body
834 movements: Coordinate structure of perspective space. *Perception* 23, 1447-1455. doi:
835 10.1068/p231447

- 836 Renner, R. S., Velichkovsky, B. M., and Helmert, J. R. (2013). The perception of egocentric
837 distances in virtual environments-a review. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 46, 1-40. doi:
838 10.1145/2543581.2543590
- 839 Riecke, B. E., Cunningham, D. W., and Bühlhoff, H. H. (2007). Spatial updating in virtual reality:
840 The sufficiency of visual information. *Psychol. Res. – Psych. Fo.* 71, 298-313. doi: 10.1007/s00426-
841 006-0085-z
- 842 Rieser, J. J. (1989). Access to knowledge of spatial structure at novel points of observation. *J. Exp.*
843 *Psychol. Learn.* 15, 1157-1165. doi: 10.1037/0278-7393.15.6.1157
- 844 Ruddle, R. A., and Lessels, S. (2006). For efficient navigational search, humans require full physical
845 movement, but not a rich visual scene. *Psychol. Sci.* 17, 460-465. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-
846 9280.2006.01728.x
- 847 Shelton, A. L., and McNamara, T. P. (2001). Systems of spatial reference in human memory.
848 *Cognitive Psychol.* 43, 274-310. doi: 10.1006/cogp.2001.0758
- 849 Sjolund, L. A., Kelly, J. W., and McNamara, T. P. (2018). Optimal combination of environmental
850 cues and path integration during navigation. *Mem. Cognition* 46, 89-99. doi: 10.3758/s13421-017-
851 0747-7
- 852 Suzuki, R., Karim, A., Xia, T., Hedayati, H., and Marquardt, N. (2022). “Augmented reality and
853 robotics: A survey and taxonomy for AR-enhanced human-robot interaction and robotic interfaces,”
854 in *CHI '22: Proceedings of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*
855 (ACM), article no. 553. doi: 10.1145/3491102.3517719
- 856 Vienne, C., Masfrand, S., Bourdin, C., and Vercher, J. L. (2020). Depth perception in virtual reality
857 systems: Effect of screen distance, environment richness and display factors. *IEEE Access* 8, 29099-
858 29110. doi: 1109/ACCESS.2020.2972122
- 859 von der Heyde, M., and Riecke, B. E. (2002). “Embedding presence-related terminology in a logical
860 and functional model,” in *Presence 2002*, ed. F. R. Gouveia (Porto: Universidare Fernando Pessoa),
861 37-52.
862 <http://matthewlombard.com/ISPR/Proceedings/2002/von%20der%20Heyde%20and%20Riecke.pdf>
- 863 Wang, R. F. (2017). Spatial updating and common misinterpretations of spatial reference frames.
864 *Spat. Cogn. Comput.* 17, 222-249. doi: 10.1080/13875868.2017.1304394
- 865 Wolbers, T., Hegarty, M., Büchel, C., and Loomis, J. M. (2008). Spatial updating: How the brain
866 keeps track of changing object locations during observer motion. *Nat. Neurosci.* 11, 1223-1230. doi:
867 10.1038/nn.2189
- 868 Wraga, M., Creem-Regehr, S. H., and Proffitt, D. R. (2004). Spatial updating of virtual displays.
869 *Mem. Cognition* 32, 399–415. doi: 10.3758/BF03195834
- 870 Zhou, R., and Mou, W. (2019). Boundary shapes guide selection of reference points in goal
871 localization. *Atten. Percept. Psycho.* 81, 2482-2498. doi: 10.3758/s13414-019-01776-7

872

873 **13 Tables**

874 TABLE 1. Target locations in Experiment 1.

Target Location	Left	(x, y)	Right	(x, y)
1	L1	(-6, 17)	R1	(6, 17)
2	L2	(-3, 15)	R2	(3, 15)
3	L3	(-3, 13)	R3	(3, 13)
4	L4	(-6, 11)	R4	(6, 11)

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877 TABLE 2. Parameter estimates of intercepts for bias on the x-axis and on the forward y-axis and
 878 rotation angles of response point clouds in Experiment 1.

	PSRF	ESS	Mode	HDI low	HDI high
Target Location 1 (L1/R1)					
β_{x0} Intercept	1.00	124216	-1.39	-1.45	-1.33
β_{y0} Intercept	1.00	137363	-2.01	-2.11	-1.92
θ Same Side	1.00	84336	15.72	10.76	20.54
θ Opposite	1.00	80750	15.99	12.26	19.57
θ No Wall	1.00	80920	14.67	10.17	19.20
Target Location 2 (L2/R2)					
β_{x0} Intercept	1.00	132341	-0.02	-0.07	0.02
β_{y0} Intercept	1.00	138598	-1.36	-1.45	-1.26
θ Same Side	1.00	79770	14.39	10.15	18.27
θ Opposite	1.00	91731	3.63	0.82	6.25
θ No Wall	1.00	91834	4.48	1.18	7.67
Target Location 3 (L3/R3)					
β_{x0} Intercept	1.00	143383	-0.00002	-0.04	0.04
β_{y0} Intercept	1.00	146976	-0.70	-0.79	-0.61
θ Same Side	1.00	88253	7.77	3.63	12.19
θ Opposite	1.00	90820	4.10	0.31	8.03
θ No Wall	1.00	88402	4.42	1.34	7.52
Target Location 4 (L4/R4)					
β_{x0} Intercept	1.00	146452	-1.20	-1.27	-1.14
β_{y0} Intercept	1.00	125513	-0.11	-0.19	-0.02
θ Same Side	1.00	89702	29.25	18.05	40.29
θ Opposite	1.00	88757	7.22	-1.69	16.79
θ No Wall	1.00	92934	6.33	-0.51	13.35

PSRF: Potential Scale Reduction Factor, ESS: Effective Sample Size, HDI low and HDI high: Lower and upper boundaries of 95% highest density intervals

880 TABLE 3. Target locations in Experiment 2.

Target Location	Left	(x, y)	Right	(x, y)
1	L1	(-1.5, 15.67)	R1	(1.5, 15.67)
2	L2	(-3.5, 18.01)	R2	(3.5, 18.01)
3 Rectangle	L3	(-5.5, 17.16)	R3	(5.5, 17.16)
3 Trapezoid, Ellipse	L3	(-7.3, 15.96)	R3	(7.3, 15.96)
4	L4	(-5.5, 13.87)	R4	(5.5, 13.87)

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883 TABLE 4. Parameter estimates of intercepts for bias on the x-axis and on the forward y-axis and
 884 rotation angles of response point clouds for the Rectangle group in Experiment 2.

	PSRF	ESS	Mode	HDI low	HDI high
Target 1					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	129707	-0.11	-0.14	-0.07
by0 Intercept	1.00	38163	-0.63	-0.74	-0.53
θ Landmarks	1.00	88772	5.51	0.19	10.47
θ Boundary	1.00	76646	4.68	2.36	7.00
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	90754	5.80	-0.25	11.64
Target 2					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	85776	-0.23	-0.27	-0.18
by0 Intercept	1.00	84138	-0.92	-1.05	-0.80
θ Landmarks	1.00	70924	15.41	12.26	18.51
θ Boundary	1.00	66306	12.50	9.64	15.17
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	65058	12.96	10.75	15.43
Target 3					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	61914	-0.51	-0.58	-0.44
by0 Intercept	1.00	55332	-0.74	-0.87	-0.62
θ Landmarks	1.00	83519	22.84	14.26	31.20
θ Boundary	1.00	82322	21.16	18.62	23.94
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	77774	21.74	18.06	25.19
Target 4					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	125052	-0.40	-0.46	-0.33
by0 Intercept	1.00	112649	-0.46	-0.57	-0.35
θ Landmarks	1.00	89655	29.64	21.03	37.64
θ Boundary	1.00	72447	18.18	13.47	22.77
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	79136	18.39	11.28	26.08

PSRF: Potential Scale Reduction Factor, ESS: Effective Sample Size, HDI low and HDI high: Lower and upper boundaries of 95% highest density intervals

886 TABLE 5. Parameter estimates of intercepts for bias on the x-axis and on the forward y-axis and
 887 rotation angles of response point clouds for the Trapezoid group in Experiment 2.

	PSRF	ESS	Mode	HDI low	HDI high
Target 1					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	107469	-0.13	-0.17	-0.09
by0 Intercept	1.00	40146	-0.38	-0.50	-0.27
θ Landmarks	1.00	76234	12.90	7.24	18.28
θ Boundary	1.00	94370	1.84	-0.61	4.55
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	76666	7.32	3.93	11.11
Target 2					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	96433	-0.29	-0.34	-0.25
by0 Intercept	1.00	94510	-0.50	-0.61	-0.40
θ Landmarks	1.00	70934	16.42	12.20	20.34
θ Boundary	1.00	70951	11.34	7.65	15.42
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	73510	15.70	11.17	20.03
Target 3					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	127495	-0.46	-0.54	-0.37
by0 Intercept	1.00	134675	-0.76	-0.88	-0.64
θ Landmarks	1.00	87594	17.28	4.29	29.46
θ Boundary	1.00	84575	13.07	1.63	24.44
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	79412	22.14	13.10	30.70
Target 4					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	128074	0.001	-0.07	0.07
by0 Intercept	1.00	89107	-0.33	-0.44	-0.23
θ Landmarks	1.00	90148	28.00	11.31	44.16
θ Boundary	1.00	77354	17.69	11.69	23.75
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	84408	15.09	2.10	29.09

PSRF: Potential Scale Reduction Factor, ESS: Effective Sample Size, HDI low and HDI high: Lower and upper boundaries of 95% highest density intervals

889 TABLE 6. Parameter estimates of intercepts for bias on the x-axis and on the forward y-axis and
 890 rotation angles of response point clouds for the Ellipse group in Experiment 2.

	PSRF	ESS	Mode	HDI low	HDI high
Target 1					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	120263	-0.04	-0.08	0.0009
by0 Intercept	1.00	53061	-0.98	-1.11	-0.85
θ Landmarks	1.00	91138	-1.89	-6.24	2.73
θ Boundary	1.00	89947	1.05	-1.68	3.93
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	78320	11.06	6.35	16.03
Target 2					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	93173	-0.20	-0.26	-0.14
by0 Intercept	1.00	107243	-1.17	-1.31	-1.03
θ Landmarks	1.00	76235	9.23	5.24	13.01
θ Boundary	1.00	77108	9.24	3.43	14.23
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	70574	12.59	9.20	15.84
Target 3					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	89846	-0.72	-0.81	-0.63
by0 Intercept	1.00	112398	-1.28	-1.41	-1.15
θ Landmarks	1.00	108221	40.59	33.57	47.04
θ Boundary	1.00	84061	11.85	4.68	19.48
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	78781	22.37	16.09	28.62
Target 4					
bx0 Intercept	1.00	135736	-0.17	-0.24	-0.10
by0 Intercept	1.00	106088	-0.53	-0.64	-0.41
θ Landmarks	1.00	80187	24.78	16.19	33.66
θ Boundary	1.00	78341	11.48	5.81	17.29
θ Boundary & Landmarks	1.00	82841	17.01	8.57	24.63

PSRF: Potential Scale Reduction Factor, ESS: Effective Sample Size, HDI low and HDI high: Lower and upper boundaries of 95% highest density intervals

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893 **14 Figures**

894

895 **FIGURE 1.** Virtual environment in Experiment 1 with a lateral wall on the right and sleepers during
896 translation.

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 899 FIGURE 2. Mean absolute distance error in Experiment 1 in trials with translation (A) and trials
 900 without translation (B). Error bars show standard errors of the mean.

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 903 FIGURE 3. Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of responses in
 904 Experiment 1.

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908 FIGURE 4. Modes and 95% HDI boundaries for deflection parameter estimates of bias on the x-axis
 909 and on the forward y-axis in Experiment 1.

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913 FIGURE 5. Modes and 95% HDI boundaries for parameter estimates of standard deviation on the x-
 914 axis and on the forward y-axis in Experiment 1.

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Target Presentation

Response

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918 FIGURE 6. Virtual environment in Experiment 2 with landmarks and a Rectangle boundary.

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922 FIGURE 7. Boundary shapes with landmarks and target locations in Experiment 2.

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926 FIGURE 8. Mean absolute distance error in Experiment 2, (A) Rectangle, (B) Trapezoid, (C) Ellipse.
 927 Error bars show standard errors of the mean.

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 931 FIGURE 9. Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of responses for the
 932 Rectangle group in Experiment 2.

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 936 FIGURE 10. Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of responses for the
 937 Trapezoid group in Experiment 2.

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 941 FIGURE 11. Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of responses for the
 942 Ellipse group in Experiment 2.

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946 FIGURE 12. Modes and 95% HDI boundaries for deflection parameter estimates of bias on the x-
 947 axis and on the forward y-axis in Experiment 2.

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951 FIGURE 13. Modes and 95% HDI boundaries for parameter estimates of standard deviation on the x-
 952 axis and on the forward y-axis in Experiment 2.

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955 **Supplementary Figure 1.** Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of
 956 responses in Experiment 1 showing the data in Figure 3 separately for left and right target locations.

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960 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of
961 responses for the Rectangle group in Experiment 2 showing the data in Figure 9 separately for left
962 and right target locations.

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966 **Supplementary Figure 3.** Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of
967 responses for the Trapezoid group in Experiment 2 showing the data in Figure 10 separately for left
968 and right target locations.

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972 **Supplementary Figure 4.** Mean response coordinates with ellipses capturing about 80% of
973 responses for the Ellipse group in Experiment 2 showing the data in Figure 11 separately for left and
974 right target locations.

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